

Case study guide: applying the ZT scenario-oriented method

This guide describes how the paper's method is applied to derive Zero Trust (ZT) oriented security scenarios from ASRs. The paper's validation corresponds to an expert-based assessment (n=2).

1. Case study objective

Assess whether the method helps derive traceable artifacts (SIGs and QAS scenarios) that support ZT-aligned architectural decisions, starting from security ASRs.

2. Participants (expert-based assessment)

Role	Profile (summary)	Responsibility in the evaluation
Expert E1	5+ years in software architecture and security	Apply the method end-to-end over the 3 ASRs and answer the Likert questionnaire.
Expert E2	5+ years in software architecture and security	Apply the method independently and answer the Likert questionnaire.

3. Inputs

- System description and its threat context (assume breach).
- List of ASRs (ASR_1 to ASR_3) and their preliminary mapping to QA.
- Reference catalogs: ZT Principles-QA and ZT Principles-Mechanisms/Techniques (IDs A3, A6, A8, A10, A11, A13, A16).
- Templates: SIG and QAS scenario template.

4. Procedure (method steps)

- 1 Step 1 - Identify relevant QA: select security QA that drive the ASRs (Confidentiality, Integrity, Auditability, Availability).
- 2 Step 2 - Decompose QA into ZT softgoal trees (SIG): model QA as a root softgoal and refine by ZT principles; then refine into operational softgoals down to concrete mechanisms.
- 3 Step 3 - Map leaf softgoals to QAS: transform leaf softgoals into scenarios (source, stimulus, artifact, environment, response, response measure), preserving traceability.

5. Expected artifacts (outputs)

- SIGs per QA/ASR: show the contribution of ZT principles and selected mechanisms.
- Set of ZT-oriented QAS scenarios (SI_1, SC_1, SA_1, SV_1).
- Traceability matrix ASR → QA → ZT Principles → Scenarios.
- Brief decision/justification record (rationale) derived from traceability.

6. Traceability matrix (excerpt)

ASR	QA	ZT Principles	Scenario
ASR_1	Integrity	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access	SI_1
ASR_1	Confidentiality	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach	SC_1
ASR_2	Auditability	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach	SA_1
ASR_3	Availability	Verify Explicitly; Least-Privilege Access; Assume Breach	SV_1

7. Quality criteria (what to review in the artifacts)

- Scenarios with verifiable measures (response measure) and unambiguous terms.
- SIGs with justified links: each mechanism must explicitly support a ZT principle and a QA.
- Domain coherence (academic system) across all narratives and examples.
- Complete traceability with no gaps (ASR → QA → ZT → mechanism → scenario).

References

Aligned with the ICSA 2026 workshop paper and its expert-based assessment (n=2).